

Yang-Lee Edge Singularity of the Infinite-Range Ising Model

Seung-Yeon Kim

Abstract—The Ising ferromagnet, consisting of magnetic spins, is the simplest system showing phase transitions and critical phenomena at finite temperatures. The Ising ferromagnet has played a central role in our understanding of phase transitions and critical phenomena. Also, the Ising ferromagnet explains the gas-liquid phase transitions accurately. In particular, the Ising ferromagnet in a nonzero magnetic field has been one of the most intriguing and outstanding unsolved problems. We study analytically the partition function zeros in the complex magnetic-field plane and the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet in an external magnetic field. In addition, we compare the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet with that of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet in an external magnetic field.

Keywords—Ising ferromagnet, Magnetic field, Partition function zeros, Yang-Lee edge singularity.

I. INTRODUCTION

PHASE transitions and critical phenomena are the most universal phenomena in nature. The two-dimensional Ising ferromagnet, consisting of magnetic spins, is the simplest system showing phase transitions and critical phenomena at finite temperatures. The Ising ferromagnet has played a central role [1] in our understanding of phase transitions and critical phenomena since the Onsager (Nobel prize winner in 1968) solution [2] of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet in the absence of an external magnetic field. In addition, the Ising ferromagnet explains the gas-liquid phase transitions exactly. However, the Ising ferromagnet in a nonzero magnetic field has been one of the most intriguing and outstanding unsolved problems except for the trivial one-dimensional Ising ferromagnet [3]–[6].

Phase transitions and critical phenomena can be understood based on the concept of partition function zeros. Yang and Lee (Nobel prize winners in 1957) [7] proposed a rigorous mechanism for the occurrence of phase transitions in the thermodynamic limit and yielded an insight into the unsolved problem of the ferromagnetic Ising ferromagnet at arbitrary temperature (T) in a magnetic field (B) by introducing the concept of the zeros of the grand partition function $Z(T, B)$ (for fluid systems, $Z(T, \mu)$ as a function of chemical potential μ) in the complex magnetic-field (for fluid systems, chemical potential) plane (the so-called Yang-Lee zeros). They [8] also formulated the celebrated circle theorem, which states that the Yang-Lee zeros of the Ising ferromagnet lie on the unit circle $x_0 = e^{i\theta}$ in the complex fugacity ($x = e^{-2B/k_B T}$) plane.

S.-Y. Kim is with the School of Liberal Arts and Sciences, Korea National University of Transportation, Chungju 380-702, Republic of Korea (e-mail: sykimm@ut.ac.kr).

At the Curie temperature T_c , Yang-Lee zeros cut the positive real axis at the point $x_c = 1$ ($B_c = 0$) in the thermodynamic limit. The spontaneous magnetization m_0 is determined by the density of Yang-Lee zeros $g(\theta)$ on the positive real axis, i.e., $m_0 = 2\pi g(\theta = 0)$. Above T_c , Yang-Lee zeros do not cut the positive real axis in the thermodynamic limit. There is a gap in the distribution of zeros around the positive real axis; that is, $g(\theta) = 0$ for $|\theta| < \theta_e$. For $T > T_c$, the Yang-Lee zeros at $\theta = \pm\theta_e$ are called the Yang-Lee edge singularities, and their locations depend on temperature. It is well known that $\theta_e = 0$ at T_c and $\theta_e = \pi$ at $T = \infty$ [9]. However, for $T_c < T < \infty$, the location of the Yang-Lee edge singularity $\theta_e(T)$ has never been determined except for the one-dimensional Ising ferromagnet.

The Yang-Lee edge singularity provides key information for finding the unknown equation of state of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet in a nonzero magnetic field. Therefore, the Yang-Lee edge singularity has been studied extensively for the Ising ferromagnet [10]–[20]. Kortman and Griffiths [10] carried out the first systematic investigation of Yang-Lee zeros for the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet by using a high field, high-temperature series expansion. They found that the density of Yang-Lee zeros for the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet diverges at the Yang-Lee edge singularity θ_e for high temperatures. Fisher [11] proposed the ideas that the Yang-Lee edge singularity could be thought of as a new second-order phase transition with associated critical exponents and that the Yang-Lee edge singularity could be considered as a conventional critical point. The critical point of the Yang-Lee edge singularity is associated with a ϕ^3 theory. The crossover dimension of the Yang-Lee edge singularity is $d_c = 6$. The Yang-Lee edge singularity has also been investigated for the two-dimensional Ising ferromagnet FeCl_2 in axial magnetic fields experimentally [17].

Following Yang and Lee's idea, Fisher [21] introduced the partition function zeros in the complex temperature plane (the so-called Fisher zeros) utilizing the Onsager solution of the square-lattice Ising model in the absence of an external magnetic field. Fisher also showed that the partition function zeros in the complex temperature plane of the square-lattice Ising model determine its ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic critical temperatures in the absence an external magnetic field at the same time. However, there exists no circle theorem for partition function zeros in the complex temperature plane, and studying partition function zeros in the complex temperature plane is a difficult task.

By calculating the partition function zeros and examining the behavior of the first partition function zero (partition

function zero closest to the positive real axis), phase transitions and critical phenomena can be much more clearly understood. Because the partition function zeros of a given system provide valuable information on its exact solution, earlier studies on partition function zeros were mainly performed in the fields of mathematical physics and rigorous statistical mechanics. Nowadays, the concept of partition function zeros is applied to all fields of physics from particle physics to biophysics, and they are popularly used as one of the most effective methods to determine the critical points and exponents [22]–[58].

In this work, we study analytically the partition function zeros in the complex magnetic-field plane and the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet in an external magnetic field. Also, we compare the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet with that of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet in an external magnetic field.

II. INFINITE-RANGE ISING MODEL

The infinite-range Ising ferromagnet with N (magnetic) spins in an external magnetic field B is defined by the Hamiltonian [58]–[60]

$$\mathcal{H} = -\frac{J}{N} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \sigma_i \sigma_j - B \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i, \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_i = \pm 1$, J is the coupling constant ($J > 0$), and the first term indicates a sum over all possible bonds

$$N_b = \frac{1}{2}N(N-1) \quad (2)$$

between two different spins σ_i and σ_j . If there is a spin configuration with r down ($\sigma_i = -1$) spins and $N - r$ up ($\sigma_i = 1$) spins, the magnetization M is defined by

$$M \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i = (N - r) - r = N - 2r. \quad (3)$$

Also, the first sum of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \sigma_i \sigma_j \\ &= \frac{1}{2}r(r-1) + \frac{1}{2}(N-r)(N-r-1) - r(N-r) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(M^2 - N). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the Hamiltonian for a spin configuration with r down spins and $N - r$ up spins is simply expressed as

$$\mathcal{H} = -\frac{J}{2N}(M^2 - N) - BM. \quad (5)$$

The partition function (a sum over all 2^N spin states) of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet

$$Z = \sum_{\{\sigma_n\}} e^{-\beta\mathcal{H}}, \quad (6)$$

TABLE I
PARTITION FUNCTION ZEROS IN THE COMPLEX MAGNETIC-FIELD
($x = e^{-2\beta B}$) PLANE OF THE INFINITE-RANGE ISING FERROMAGNET FOR
 $N = 20$ AT THE CURIE TEMPERATURE $T_c = J/k_B$

-0.991616971016042 - 0.129212161939080i
-0.991616971016042 + 0.129212161939080i
-0.925154056403051 - 0.379591849123476i
-0.925154056403051 + 0.379591849123476i
-0.795430982323641 - 0.606044183504509i
-0.795430982323641 + 0.606044183504509i
-0.608834977858797 - 0.793296898856713i
-0.608834977858797 + 0.793296898856713i
-0.374912562575763 - 0.927060176268442i
-0.374912562575763 + 0.927060176268442i
-0.106367073277723 - 0.994326931005256i
-0.106367073277723 + 0.994326931005256i
0.180851554735243 - 0.983510404189933i
0.180851554735243 + 0.983510404189933i
0.467185921263300 - 0.884159100486650i
0.467185921263300 + 0.884159100486650i
0.728276230555473 - 0.685283687247779i
0.728276230555473 + 0.685283687247779i
0.930316724674649 - 0.366757129161293i
0.930316724674649 + 0.366757129161293i

where $\beta = 1/k_B T$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T is temperature, can be written as

$$Z = \sum_{r=0}^N \binom{N}{r} \exp \left[\frac{\beta J}{2N} (M^2 - N) + \beta B M \right]. \quad (7)$$

And the free energy F is given by

$$F = -k_B T \ln Z. \quad (8)$$

III. PARTITION FUNCTION ZEROS

The partition function is also expressed as

$$Z = \exp \left[\frac{\beta J}{2N} (N^2 - N) + \beta B N \right] \sum_{r=0}^N \binom{N}{r} y^{r(N-r)} x^r, \quad (9)$$

where y is the low-temperature variable and x is the fugacity variable, defined by

$$y \equiv \exp \left[-\frac{2\beta J}{N} \right] \quad (10)$$

and

$$x \equiv \exp[-2\beta B]. \quad (11)$$

Then, the reduced partition function

$$\bar{Z} = \sum_{r=0}^N \binom{N}{r} y^{r(N-r)} x^r \quad (12)$$

is a polynomial in variables y and x . That is, equation (12) determines the partition function zeros of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet.

TABLE II

YANG-LEE EDGE SINGULARITY x_e OF THE INFINITE-RANGE ISING FERROMAGNET AT THE CURIE TEMPERATURE $T_c = J/k_B$ FOR $N = 20 \sim 160$

N	x_e
20	$0.930316724674649 + 0.366757129161293i$
30	$0.961275775929932 + 0.275588248316772i$
40	$0.974554786275155 + 0.224149433521897i$
50	$0.981653381379761 + 0.190674169267056i$
60	$0.985966142256138 + 0.166945399231453i$
70	$0.988816229521337 + 0.149139076821627i$
80	$0.990815402977553 + 0.135221437732441i$
90	$0.992281546821177 + 0.124005370198921i$
100	$0.993394561919970 + 0.114748613707665i$
110	$0.994263131699981 + 0.106961791973334i$
120	$0.994956396771223 + 0.100308367168573i$
130	$0.995520225970465 + 0.094548821693947i$
140	$0.995986125280646 + 0.089507755241911i$
150	$0.996376378112817 + 0.085053589805401i$
160	$0.996707144074488 + 0.081085565613602i$

Table I shows the the partition function zeros in the complex magnetic-field ($x = e^{-2\beta B}$) plane of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet for $N = 20$ at the Curie temperature $T_c = J/k_B$, obtained from (12). As shown in the table, the partition function zeros always have their complex conjugates to make the real partition function and the number of the partition function zeros is equal to N . The partition function zero $x_e = 0.930316724674649 + 0.366757129161293i$ (its complex conjugate $0.930316724674649 - 0.366757129161293i$) lies closest to the positive real axis, and it is the Yang-Lee edge singularity. Table II shows the Yang-Lee edge singularity x_e of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet at the Curie temperature $T_c = J/k_B$ for $N = 20 \sim 160$.

IV. EQUATION OF STATE

The density of state $\Omega(M)$ for the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(M) &= \binom{N}{r} = \frac{N!}{(N-r)!r!} \\ &= \frac{N!}{[\frac{1}{2}(N+M)]![\frac{1}{2}(N-M)]!} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

And the unitless entropy $S(M)$ is written as

$$S(M) = \ln \Omega = \ln N! - \ln \left[\frac{1}{2}(N+M) \right]! - \ln \left[\frac{1}{2}(N-M) \right]! \quad (14)$$

For large N , using Stirling's formula for the factorial

$$\ln N! = N \ln N - N, \quad (15)$$

we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dM} \ln \left[\frac{1}{2}(N \pm M) \right]! = \pm \frac{1}{2} \ln \left[\frac{1}{2}(N \pm M) \right]. \quad (16)$$

TABLE III

EXACT VALUES FOR THE YANG-LEE EDGE SINGULARITY $x_e(T)$ AND ITS ARGUMENT $\theta_e(T)$ OF THE INFINITE-RANGE ISING FERROMAGNET IN THE THERMODYNAMIC LIMIT

T/T_c	x_e	θ_e
1.5	$0.958771114 + 0.28417935i$	0.288150
2	$0.84147098 + 0.54030231i$	0.570796
2.5	$0.70216810 + 0.71201121i$	0.792358
3	$0.56709298 + 0.82365378i$	0.967824
3.5	$0.44448284 + 0.89578736i$	1.110199
4	$0.33577382 + 0.94194264i$	1.228370
5	$0.15586085 + 0.98777902i$	1.414297
10	$-0.32148301 + 0.94691535i$	1.898092
20	$-0.63180497 + 0.77512739i$	2.254676

Thus, the derivative of the entropy is simply given by

$$\frac{d}{dM} S(M) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{N-M}{N+M}. \quad (17)$$

The restricted partition function $z(M)$ is defined by

$$z(M) \equiv \binom{N}{r} \exp \left[\frac{\beta J}{2N} (M^2 - N) + \beta B M \right]. \quad (18)$$

Then, the derivative of $\ln Z(M)$ is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dM} z(M) &= \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{N-M}{N+M} + \frac{\beta J M}{N} + \beta B \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{1-m}{1+m} + \beta J m + \beta B, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $m \equiv \frac{M}{N}$ is the magnetization per volume. The optimal condition

$$\frac{d}{dM} z(M) = 0 \quad (20)$$

yields

$$\ln \frac{1-m}{1+m} = -2\beta(Jm + B). \quad (21)$$

Finally, we reach the equation of state

$$m = \tanh \beta(Jm + B) \quad (22)$$

for the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet in the thermodynamic limit [58]–[60].

V. YANG-LEE EDGE SINGULARITY

From the equation of state, the critical temperature T_c (the so-called Curie temperature) for $B = 0$ is given by

$$\beta_c J = 1, \quad (23)$$

equivalently,

$$T_c = \frac{J}{k_B}. \quad (24)$$

Differentiating the equation of state with respect to m , we obtain the useful relation

$$1 = \beta J [1 - \tanh^2 \beta(Jm + B)] = \beta J (1 - m^2), \quad (25)$$

TABLE IV

ARGUMENT OF THE YANG-LEE EDGE SINGULARITY FOR THE SQUARE-LATTICE ISING FERROMAGNET IN THE THERMODYNAMIC LIMIT, ACCURATELY ESTIMATED FROM THE EXACT PARTITION FUNCTION ZEROS FOR FINITE LATTICES

T/T_c	θ_e
1.5	0.18544 ± 0.00009
2	0.42578 ± 0.00004
2.5	0.63180 ± 0.00003
3	0.80234 ± 0.00002
3.5	0.94444 ± 0.00002
4	1.06449 ± 0.00002
5	1.25667 ± 0.00001
10	1.771000 ± 0.000008
20	2.159285 ± 0.000005

from which the spontaneous magnetization (per volume)

$$m_0(T) = \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{k_B T}{J}} = \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{T}{T_c}} \quad (26)$$

is derived.

In the thermodynamic limit, the equation of state determines the Yang-Lee edge singularity x_e of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet according to the following equation

$$x_e(T) = \exp[-2\beta B_e] = \exp[2(\beta J m_0 - \tanh^{-1} m_0)] \quad (27)$$

for $T > T_c$. Hence, the argument of the Yang-Lee edge singularity is given by

$$\theta_e(T) = -i \ln x_e(T). \quad (28)$$

Table III shows the exact values for the Yang-Lee edge singularity and its argument of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet in the thermodynamic limit. As shown in the table, the Yang-Lee edge singularity is not far from the point $x = 1$ ($\theta = 0$) in low temperature. As temperature increases, it moves away and approaches $x = -1$ ($\theta = \pi$).

For comparison, we also show the argument of the Yang-Lee edge singularity for the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet in the thermodynamic limit, accurately estimated from the exact partition function zeros for finite lattices [20], as shown in Table IV. The error estimates are twice the difference between the $(n-1, 1)$ and $(n-1, 2)$ approximants of the Bulirsch-Stoer extrapolation method [61]. Until now, the exact values for the Yang-Lee edge singularity and its argument of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet have never been known. Clearly, we notice that the argument of the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet is larger than that of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet, as shown in the table.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Ising ferromagnet, consisting of magnetic spins, is the simplest system showing phase transitions and critical phenomena at finite temperatures. The Ising ferromagnet in a nonzero magnetic field has been one of the most intriguing and outstanding unsolved problems. The partition function

zeros in the complex magnetic-field plane (shortly, the Yang-Lee zeros) of the Ising ferromagnet has played a central role in understanding its properties in a nonzero magnetic field. Above the Curie temperature, the Yang-Lee zero at the edge of the zero distribution of the Ising ferromagnet is called the Yang-Lee edge singularity. The Yang-Lee edge singularity has been indispensable in investigating the unknown properties of the Ising ferromagnet in a nonzero magnetic field. We have studied analytically the partition function zeros in the complex magnetic-field plane and the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet in an external magnetic field. In addition, we have compared the Yang-Lee edge singularity of the infinite-range Ising ferromagnet with that of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet in an external magnetic field.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author is grateful to Prof. R. J. Creswick for very useful discussions. This research was supported by Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by the Ministry of Education (grant number NRF-2014R1A1A2056127).

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Domb, *The Critical Point*, Taylor and Francis, London, 1996.
- [2] L. Onsager, "Crystal statistics. I. A two-dimensional model with an order-disorder transition", *Physical Review*, 65 (1944) 117-149.
- [3] S.-Y. Kim, "Yang-Lee zeros of the one-dimensional Q -state Potts model", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 44 (2004) 495-500.
- [4] S.-Y. Kim, "Fisher zeros and Potts zeros of the Q -state Potts model in a magnetic field", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 45 (2004) 302-309.
- [5] J. Lee, "Low-temperature behavior of the finite-size one-dimensional Ising model and the partition function zeros", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 65 (2014) 676-683.
- [6] S.-Y. Kim, "Generalized Schottky anomaly", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 65 (2014) 970-972.
- [7] C. N. Yang and T. D. Lee, "Statistical theory of equations of state and phase transitions. I. Theory of condensation", *Physical Review*, 87 (1952) 404-409.
- [8] T. D. Lee and C. N. Yang, "Statistical theory of equations of state and phase transitions. II. Lattice gas and Ising model", *Physical Review*, 87 (1952) 410-419.
- [9] S.-Y. Kim and R. J. Creswick, "Yang-Lee zeros of the Q -state Potts model in the complex magnetic field plane", *Physical Review Letters*, 81 (1998) 2000-2003.
- [10] P. J. Kortman and R. B. Griffiths, "Density of zeros on the Lee-Yang circle for two Ising ferromagnets", *Physical Review Letters*, 27 (1971) 1439-1442.
- [11] M. E. Fisher, "Yang-Lee edge singularity and ϕ^3 field theory", *Physical Review Letters*, 40 (1978) 1610-1613.
- [12] G. A. Baker, M. E. Fisher, and P. Moussa, "Yang-Lee edge singularity in the hierarchical model", *Physical Review Letters*, 42 (1979) 615-618.
- [13] K. Uzelac, P. Pfeuty, and R. Jullien, "Yang-Lee edge singularity from a real-space renormalization-group method", *Physical Review Letters*, 43 (1979) 805-808.
- [14] G. Parisi and N. Sourlas, "Critical behavior of branched polymers and the Lee-Yang edge singularity", *Physical Review Letters*, 46 (1981) 871-874.
- [15] D. Dhar, "Exact solution of a directed-site animals-enumeration problem in three dimensionals", *Physical Review Letters*, 51 (1983) 853-856.
- [16] J. L. Cardy, "Conformal invariance and the Yang-Lee edge singularity in two dimensionals", *Physical Review Letters*, 54 (1985) 1354-1356.
- [17] C. Binek, "Density of zeros on the Lee-Yang circle obtained from magnetization data of a two-dimensional Ising ferromagnet", *Physical Review Letters*, 81 (1998) 5644-5647.
- [18] S.-Y. Kim, "Density of Yang-Lee zeros and Yang-Lee edge singularity for the antiferromagnetic Ising model", *Nuclear Physics B*, 705 (2005) 504-520.

- [19] S.-Y. Kim, "Density of Yang-Lee zeros for the Ising ferromagnet", *Physical Review E*, 74 (2006) 011119:1-7.
- [20] S.-Y. Kim, "Yang-Lee edge singularity of the square-lattice Ising ferromagnet", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 59 (2011) 2205-2208.
- [21] M. E. Fisher, "The nature of critical points," in *Lectures in Theoretical Physics*, vol. 7c, W. E. Brittin, Ed. Boulder: University of Colorado Press, 1965, pp. 1-159.
- [22] R. J. Creswick and S.-Y. Kim, "Finite-size scaling of the density of zeros of the partition function in first- and second-order phase transitions", *Physical Review E*, 56 (1997) 2418-2422.
- [23] S.-Y. Kim and R. J. Creswick, "Fisher zeros of the Q -state Potts model in the complex temperature plane for nonzero external magnetic field", *Physical Review E*, 58 (1998) 7006-7012.
- [24] R. J. Creswick and S.-Y. Kim, "Microcanonical transfer matrix study of the Q -state Potts model", *Computer Physics Communications*, 121 (1999) 26-29.
- [25] S.-Y. Kim and R. J. Creswick, "Exact results for the zeros of the partition function of the Potts model on finite lattices", *Physica A*, 281 (2000) 252-261.
- [26] S.-Y. Kim, R. J. Creswick, C.-N. Chen, and C.-K. Hu, "Partition function zeros of the Q -state Potts model for non-integer Q ", *Physica A*, 281 (2000) 262-267.
- [27] S.-Y. Kim and R. J. Creswick, "Density of states, Potts zeros, and Fisher zeros of the Q -state Potts model for continuous Q ", *Physical Review E*, 63 (2001) 066107:1-12.
- [28] W. Janke and R. Kenna, "The strength of first and second order phase transitions from partition function zeroes", *Journal of Statistical Physics*, 102 (2001) 1211-1227.
- [29] B. P. Dolan, W. Janke, D. A. Johnston, and M. Stathakopoulos, "Thin Fisher zeros", *Journal of Physics A*, 34 (2001) 6211-6223.
- [30] S.-Y. Kim, "Partition function zeros of the Q -state Potts model on the simple-cubic lattice", *Nuclear Physics B*, 637 (2002) 409-426.
- [31] S.-Y. Kim, "Yang-Lee zeros of the antiferromagnetic Ising model", *Physical Review Letters*, 93 (2004) 130604:1-4.
- [32] S.-Y. Kim, "Density of the Fisher zeros for the three-state and four-state Potts models", *Physical Review E*, 70 (2004) 016110:1-5.
- [33] S.-Y. Kim, "Fisher zeros of the Ising antiferromagnet in an arbitrary nonzero magnetic field plane", *Physical Review E*, 71 (2005) 017102:1-4.
- [34] I. Bena, M. Droz, and A. Lipowski, "Statistical mechanics of equilibrium and nonequilibrium phase transitions: The Yang-Lee formalism", *International Journal of Modern Physics B*, 19 (2005) 4269-4329.
- [35] S.-Y. Kim, "Honeycomb-lattice antiferromagnetic Ising model in a magnetic field", *Physics Letters A*, 358 (2006) 245-250.
- [36] J. L. Monroe and S.-Y. Kim, "Phase diagram and critical exponent ν for the nearest-neighbor and next-nearest-neighbor interaction Ising model", *Physical Review E*, 76 (2007) 021123:1-5.
- [37] C.-O. Hwang, S.-Y. Kim, D. Kang, and J. M. Kim, "Ising antiferromagnets in a nonzero uniform magnetic field", *Journal of Statistical Mechanics*, 7 (2007) L05001:1-8.
- [38] X.-Z. Wang, "Yang-Lee circle theorem for an ideal pseudospin-1/2 Bose gas in an arbitrary external potential and in an external magnetic field", *Physica A*, 380 (2007) 163-171.
- [39] S.-Y. Kim, C.-O. Hwang, and J. M. Kim, "Partition function zeros of the antiferromagnetic Ising model on triangular lattice in the complex temperature plane for nonzero magnetic field", *Nuclear Physics B*, 805 (2008) 441-450.
- [40] N. Ananikian, L. Ananikian, R. Artuso, and K. Sargsyan, "The partition function zeros for a Potts model of helix-coil transition with three-site interactions", *Physica A*, 387 (2008) 5433-5439.
- [41] S.-Y. Kim, "Specific heat of the square-lattice Ising antiferromagnet in a magnetic field", *Journal of Physical Studies*, 13 (2009) 4006:1-3.
- [42] P. R. Crompton, "The partition function zeroes of quantum critical points", *Nuclear Physics B*, 810 (2009) 542-562.
- [43] S.-Y. Kim, "Partition function zeros of the square-lattice Ising model with nearest- and next-nearest-neighbor interactions", *Physical Review E*, 81 (2010) 031120:1-7.
- [44] S.-Y. Kim, "Partition function zeros of the honeycomb-lattice Ising antiferromagnet in the complex magnetic-field plane", *Physical Review E*, 82 (2010) 041107:1-7.
- [45] S.-Y. Kim, "Honeycomb-lattice Ising model in a nonzero magnetic field: Low-temperature series analysis and partition function zeros", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 56 (2010) 1051-1054.
- [46] J. H. Lee, S.-Y. Kim, and J. Lee, "Exact partition function zeros and the collapse transition of a two-dimensional lattice polymer", *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 133 (2010) 114106:1-6.
- [47] J. H. Lee, H. S. Song, J. M. Kim, and S.-Y. Kim, "Study of a square-lattice Ising superantiferromagnet using the Wang-Landau algorithm and partition function zeros", *Journal of Statistical Mechanics*, 10 (2010) P03020:1-9.
- [48] C.-O. Hwang and S.-Y. Kim, "Yang-Lee zeros of triangular Ising antiferromagnets", *Physica A*, 389 (2010) 5650-5654.
- [49] D. Dalmazi and F. L. Sa, "Generalized partition function zeros of 1D spin models and their critical behavior at edge singularities", *Journal of Physics A*, 43 (2010) 255002:1-20.
- [50] J. H. Lee, S.-Y. Kim, and J. Lee, "Collapse transition of a square-lattice polymer with next nearest-neighbor interaction", *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 135 (2011) 204102:1-4.
- [51] S.-Y. Kim, "Triangular-lattice Ising model in a nonzero magnetic field", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 58 (2011) 5-8.
- [52] S.-Y. Kim, "Specific heat and partition function zeros of the three-state Potts model", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 59 (2011) 2980-2983.
- [53] J. H. Lee, S.-Y. Kim, and J. Lee, "Exact partition function zeros of a polymer on a simple cubic lattice", *Physical Review E*, 86 (2012) 011802:1-7.
- [54] J. L. Lebowitz, D. Ruelle, and E. R. Speer, "Location of the Lee-Yang zeros and absence of phase transitions in some Ising spin systems", *Journal of Mathematical Physics*, 53 (2012) 095211:1-13.
- [55] S.-Y. Kim, "Exact partition functions of the Ising model on $L \times L$ square lattices with free boundary conditions up to $L = 22$ ", *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 62 (2013) 214-219.
- [56] J. H. Lee, S.-Y. Kim, and J. Lee, "Partition function zeros of a square-lattice homopolymer with nearest- and next-nearest-neighbor interactions", *Physical Review E*, 87 (2013) 052601:1-6.
- [57] J. Lee, "Exact partition function zeros of the Wako-Saito-Munoz-Eaton protein model", *Physical Review Letters*, 110 (2013) 248101:1-5.
- [58] Z. Glumac and Uzelac, "Yang-Lee zeros and the critical behavior of the infinite-range two- and three-state Potts models", *Physical Review E*, 87 (2013) 022140:1-10.
- [59] R. J. Baxter, *Exactly Solved Models in Statistical Mechanics*, Academic Press, London, 1982.
- [60] H. Gould and J. Tobochnik, *Statistical and Thermal Physics with Computer Applications*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, 2010.
- [61] R. Bulirsch and J. Stoer, "Fehlerabschätzungen und extrapolation mit rationalen funktionen bei verfahren vom Richardson-typus", *Numerische Mathematik*, 6 (1964) 413-427; "Numerical treatment of ordinary differential equations by extrapolation methods", *Numerische Mathematik*, 8 (1966) 1-13.